

ISic0297

Inscribed base of a dedication to Venus Victrix

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.03.20

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla Gereatis

Place of origin (modern)

Paternò

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 354

Physical Description

oval
A small
hexagonal base, with moulding at top and bottom. An
cavity is visible in the top surface into which the
original votive statue will have been
inserted.

Dimensions

Height 37.4 cm

Width 17.3 cm

Depth 23 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-10: 12-29 mm

Interlineation

Line line1 to line1 : mm

Text

1. Vener

2. ri

3. Victri

4. ci ·

5. Hyblen

6. si ·

7. C (aius) Public (ius) Dona tus
10. d (ono) · d (edit)

Apparatus

Text of Prag based on autopsy

Translation (en)

(Dedicated to) Venus Victrix Hyblensis. Caius Publicius Donatus gave this as a gift.

Translation (it)

Alla Venere Vincitrice ibleense Caio Publicio Donato offrì in dono.

Commentary

This statue base is the only Latin inscription from Paternò, and is important both for its dedication to Venus Victrix (Venus Victorious) and for the reference to Hybla. This is the only dedication to Venus Victrix from Sicily, although dedications are found across the Roman Empire, especially in the northern and western provinces. The epithet 'Hyblensis', 'of Hybla' provides important evidence (but not proof) for the identification of Paternò with ancient Hybla Gereatis, although at least two cities in ancient Sicily were called Hybla. The statue was already missing when the base was found, but there is good evidence for the Venus Victrix type, principally from Roman coins from the time of Julius Caesar onwards.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491509

EDCS 21900332

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0297>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4022604

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7013 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 237

Pace, B. 1945. *Arte e Civiltà della Sicilia antica. Volume terzo. Cultura e vita religiosa.* Genoa, Rome, Naples, Citta di Castello. At 508

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- Manganaro, G. 1964. Città di Sicilia e santuarii panellenici nel III e II secolo a.c.. *Historia*. 13: 414-439. At 433
- Manganaro, G. 1977. Per la storia dei culti nella Sicilia greca. *Cronache di Archeologia*. 16: 148-164. At 153
- Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 67
- Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 292
- Manganaro, G. 1996. Per una storia della chora Catania. In Gentile, B.(eds.), *Catania Antica. Atti del Convegno della S.I.S.A.C. (Catania 23-24 maggio 1992)*. Pisa. pp. 19-59. At 54
- Manganaro, G. 2000. Hybla Megala (Heraia) e Hybla Geleatis (Etnea). *Un ponte fra l'Italia e la Grecia. Atti del simposio in onore di Antonio di Vita*. Padova. pp. 149-154. At 151
- ph
- Trotta, F. 2000. I culti dell Sicilia: tra Greci e Iblei. *Un ponte fra l'Italia e la Grecia. Atti del simposio in onore di Antonio di Vita*. Padua. pp. 155-160. At 158

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0297. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334865>